

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for CD44 (UniProt ID: P16070) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence, and flow cytometry

Riham Ayoubi¹, Michael S. Biddle^{†2}, Charles Alende^{†1}, Maryam Fotouhi^{†1}, Sara González Bolívar¹, Carolyn Jones², Vincent Francis¹, Carl Laflamme^{1*} and Harvinder Virk^{2*}, NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group and ABIF consortium

[†] Authors contributed equally

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

² NIHR BRC-Respiratory, University of Leicester, Leicester, England, UK

* Corresponding authors: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca, hsv6@leicester.ac.uk

Abstract

CD44 is a transmembrane glycoprotein that modulates cell proliferation, adhesion and migration as well as immune function pathways. Here we have characterized a total of thirty-two CD44 commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence, and flow cytometry using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

P16070, *CD44*, CD44, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

CD44 is a transmembrane glycoprotein that acts as a receptor for the extracellular matrix components, hyaluronic acid (1, 2), fibronectin (3), osteopontin (4), and other ligands like the sulfated glycosaminoglycan chondroitin (5) and the secretory granule sulfated proteoglycan serglycin (6). The *CD44* gene encodes multiple isoforms by alternative splicing of exons 6-15 and the different proteins contain a large N-terminal extracellular domain, a transmembrane domain and a C-terminal cytoplasmic functional tail (7). CD44 regulates cell proliferation, migration and invasion by activating a myriad of downstream signaling pathways that contribute to many cancers' progression when dysregulated (7, 8). During inflammation, CD44 is also involved in activating lymphocytes (9). Lastly, CD44 is implicated in Alzheimer's disease (10) where patients present increased levels of the protein in the cerebral cortex (11).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (12). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein (12). Here we have characterized a total of thirty-two commercial CD44 antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturer, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of CD44 properties and functions. Twenty-three of the contributed antibodies were tested in western blot, nineteen in immunoprecipitation, twenty in immunofluorescence, and twenty-five antibodies were tested in flow cytometry.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (13) and in Table 4 of this data note (12).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cell lines (14, 15). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (16). MDA-MB-231 expresses the CD44 transcript at $9.5 \log_2$ TPM+1 which is above the average observed range of 2.5 to 6.0 \log_2 TPM+1 for other studied targets. MDA-MB-231 was identified as a suitable cell line for antibody testing here and was modified with CRISPR/Cas9 to KO the corresponding *CD44* gene (Table 1).

Antibodies were first screened in western blot by running MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO protein lysates on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with the CD44 antibodies in parallel. Most antibodies could selectively detect CD44 in this application using the MDA-MB-231 lysates. We also used the commercially available HAP1 cell line from Horizon Discovery (Table 1), which expresses the *CD44* transcript at a relatively low-level score ($2.5 \log_2 \text{TPM}+1$). Of the antibodies tested, only two demonstrated selective detection of CD44 in western blot in this low-expression context (Figure 1B and data not shown). Additionally, CD44 banding pattern and intensity varied depending on the lysis buffer used, as shown in Figure 1C, where MDA-MB231 cells were lysed with either the denaturing RIPA buffer or the native IP buffer. We selected MDA-MB-231 cells to test CD44 antibodies across the following applications.

We then assessed the capability of the antibodies to capture CD44 from MDA-MB-231 protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific CD44 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

For immunofluorescence, CD44 antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the CD44 antibodies were evaluated. Both WT and KO lines imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 3). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of WT and KO cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 3 are representative of this analysis (12).

For flow cytometry, MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO cells were labelled with distinct fluorescent dyes and combined at a 1:1 ratio. To detect cell surface CD44 epitopes, WT and KO cell lines were blocked in the same tube prior to antibody staining to reduce bias. The CD44 antibodies were then evaluated and antibody staining in both the WT and KO lines was quantified, with representative histograms presented in Figure 4. To detect intracellular CD44, both cell lines were fixed in PFA and permeabilized with saponin prior to staining (Figure 5).

In conclusion, we have screened a total of thirty-two CD44 commercial antibodies by western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence and flow cytometry by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 4 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all four applications (16). Several high-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect CD44 were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study CD44 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available CD44 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in CD44, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. CD44 experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (12). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used are listed in Table 1. Primary antibodies tested in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are listed in Table 2 and antibodies tested in flow cytometry in Table 3. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (17, 18).

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit, anti-mouse, and anti-rat antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 65-6120, 62-6520, and 31470, respectively. Peroxidase-conjugated Protein A for IP detection is from Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 12291. CoraLite Plus 555 goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse recombinant secondary antibodies are from Proteintech, cat. number RGAR003 and RGAM003, respectively. Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rat secondary antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A-21434. CoraLite Plus 647 goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse recombinant secondary antibodies are from Proteintech, cat. number RGAR005 and RGAM005, respectively. Alexa-647-conjugated goat anti-rat secondary antibody is from BioLegend, cat. number 405416. APC-conjugated mouse anti-human IgG1 secondary antibody is from Miltenyi Biotec, cat. number 130-119-857.

Antibody screening by western blot

MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three

washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/mL in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg of antibody to 500 µL of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µL of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse and rat antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

MDA-MB-231 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 $\times g$ for 15 min at 4°C. 0.2 mL aliquots at 1 mg/mL of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 mL of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels. Protein A:HRP was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.5 µg/mL.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). The nuclei were labelled with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) fluorescent stain. WT and KO cells were plated on a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL). Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary CD44 antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 \times 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/mL for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 \times 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68

x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification (19). Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Antibody screening by flow cytometry

For cell surface staining, MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO cells were detached, and six million cells were labelled with CellTracker green or violet, fluorescent dyes, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C7025 and C10094). WT and KO cells were then centrifuged at $400 \times g$ for 10 min at 4°C and resuspended in 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) (Sigma Aldrich, cat. number A9647) phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 12579099). Cell populations were then combined at a 1:1 ratio, centrifuged and blocked on ice for 30 min with with 5% goat serum (Sigma Aldrich, cat. number G6767), 1% BSA in PBS. After the blocking step 400,000 cells were aliquoted into individually labelled tubes, centrifuged and incubated in 150 μ L of 1% BSA PBS with primary CD44 antibodies for 30 min on ice. 500 μ L of 1% BSA PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed gently and centrifuged. Cells were then incubated for 30 minutes on ice with their corresponding CL647 (0.83 μ g/mL), AF647 (0.17 μ g/mL) or APC (1 in 600) - conjugated secondary antibody diluted in 150 μ L of 1% BSA PBS. 500 μ L of 1% BSA PBS was then added to each tube, gently vortexed and centrifuged. Tubes were then resuspended in 1 mL of 1% BSA PBS with 1 μ L of sytox orange (Thermo Fisher, S34861) and incubated on ice for 20 minutes. Data was then acquired using the Attune NxT flow cytometer.

After acquisition, data was analysed using FlowJo with the following gates. Single cells were selected by FSC-A vs FSC-H, then the cell population was selected by FSC-A vs SSC-A. Viable cells were identified by gating the sytox orange negative population using YL1-A vs SCC-A and within that gate, KO and WT cells were isolated by BL1-A vs VL1-A using a quadrat gate. Quantification of antibody staining was then observed in the RL1-A channel and histograms merged to demonstrate the staining intensity between the two populations. The figure was then assembled using Adobe Illustrator 2024.

For intracellular staining MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO cells were detached, and six million cells were labelled with CellTracker green or violet, fluorescent dyes, respectively. WT and KO cells were then centrifuged at $400 \times g$ for 10 min at 4°C and resuspended in 1% BSA PBS. Cell populations were then combined at a 1:1 ratio, centrifuged and fixed on ice for 20 min using 800 μ L of 4% PFA in PBS (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number J19943.K2). Following fixation, 1.2 mL of 1% BSA PBS was added to the tube, vortexed and centrifuged at $600 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C. Cells were then permeabilized in PBS with 0.1% saponin (Sigma Aldrich, cat. number 558255), for 10 min at room temperature, centrifuged at $600 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and then blocked with 5% goat serum, 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS for 30 min on ice. 400,000 cells were aliquoted into individually labelled tubes, centrifuged at $600 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and incubated in 150 μ L of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS with primary CD44 antibodies for 30 min on ice. 500

μL of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS was added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged at $600 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C . Cells were then incubated for 30 min on ice with their corresponding CL647 ($0.83\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), AF647 ($0.17\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) or APC (1 in 600) - conjugated secondary antibody diluted in $150 \mu\text{L}$ of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS. $500 \mu\text{L}$ of 1% BSA, 0.1% saponin PBS was then added to each tube, vortexed and centrifuged at $600 \times g$ 15 min at 4°C . Tubes were then resuspended in 1 mL of 1% BSA PBS and data was then acquired using the Attune NxT flow cytometer.

After acquisition, data was analysed using FlowJo with the following gates. Single cells were selected by FSC-A vs FSC-H, the cell population was selected by FSC-A vs SSC-A and then KO and WT cells were isolated by BL1-A vs VL1-A using a quadrat gate. Quantification of antibody staining was then observed in the RL1-A channel and histograms merged to demonstrate the staining intensity between the two populations. The figure was then assembled using Adobe Illustrator 2024.

Grant information

This work was supported by a grant from the Government of Canada through Genome Canada, Genome Quebec, and Ontario Genomics (grant no. OGI-210). RA is supported by a Mitacs fellowship.

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam-ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank -GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

Acknowledgment

We would like to thank the NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group for their important contribution to the creation of an open scientific ecosystem of antibody manufacturers and KO cell line suppliers, for the development of community-agreed protocols, and for their shared ideas, resources, and collaboration. Members of the group can be found below. We would also like to thank the Advanced BioImaging Facility (ABIF) consortium for their image analysis pipeline development and conduction (RRID:SCR_017697). Members of each group can be found below.

NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group: Thomas M. Durcan, Aled M. Edwards, Peter S. McPherson, Chetan Raina and Wolfgang Reintsch

ABIF consortium: Claire M. Brown and Joel Ryan

Thank you to the Structural Genomics Consortium, a registered charity (no. 1097737), for your support on this project. The Structural Genomics Consortium receives funding from Bayer AG, Boehringer Ingelheim, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Genentech, Genome Canada through Ontario Genomics Institute (grant no. OGI-196), the EU and EFPIA through the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking (EUbOPEN grant no. 875510), Janssen, Merck KGaA (also known as EMD in Canada and the United States), Pfizer and Takeda.

References

1. Yang B, Yang BL, Savani RC, Turley EA. Identification of a common hyaluronan binding motif in the hyaluronan binding proteins RHAMM, CD44 and link protein. *EMBO J.* 1994;13(2):286-96.
2. Liao HX, Lee DM, Levesque MC, Haynes BF. N-terminal and central regions of the human CD44 extracellular domain participate in cell surface hyaluronan binding. *J Immunol.* 1995;155(8):3938-45.
3. Jalkanen S, Jalkanen M. Lymphocyte CD44 binds the COOH-terminal heparin-binding domain of fibronectin. *J Cell Biol.* 1992;116(3):817-25.
4. Weber GF, Ashkar S, Glimcher MJ, Cantor H. Receptor-ligand interaction between CD44 and osteopontin (Eta-1). *Science.* 1996;271(5248):509-12.
5. Faassen AE, Schrage JA, Klein DJ, Oegema TR, Couchman JR, McCarthy JB. A cell surface chondroitin sulfate proteoglycan, immunologically related to CD44, is involved in type I collagen-mediated melanoma cell motility and invasion. *J Cell Biol.* 1992;116(2):521-31.
6. Toyama-Sorimachi N, Miyasaka M. A sulfated proteoglycan as a novel ligand for CD44. *J Dermatol.* 1994;21(11):795-801.
7. Xu H, Niu M, Yuan X, Wu K, Liu A. CD44 as a tumor biomarker and therapeutic target. *Exp Hematol Oncol.* 2020;9(1):36.
8. Weng X, Maxwell-Warburton S, Hasib A, Ma L, Kang L. The membrane receptor CD44: novel insights into metabolism. *Trends Endocrinol Metab.* 2022;33(5):318-32.
9. Jordan AR, Racine RR, Hennig MJ, Lokeshwar VB. The Role of CD44 in Disease Pathophysiology and Targeted Treatment. *Front Immunol.* 2015;6:182.
10. Dzwonek J, Wilczynski GM. CD44: molecular interactions, signaling and functions in the nervous system. *Front Cell Neurosci.* 2015;9:175.
11. Akiyama H, Tooyama I, Kawamata T, Ikeda K, McGeer PL. Morphological diversities of CD44 positive astrocytes in the cerebral cortex of normal subjects and patients with Alzheimer's disease. *Brain Res.* 1993;632(1-2):249-59.
12. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Gonzalez Bolivar S, Alende C, Ruiz Moleon V, Fotouhi M, et al. A consensus platform for antibody characterization. *Nat Protoc.* 2024.
13. Biddle MS, Virk HS. YCharOS open antibody characterisation data: Lessons learned and progress made F1000Research 2023. 2023;12:1344.
14. Laflamme C, McKeever PM, Kumar R, Schwartz J, Kolahdouzan M, Chen CX, et al. Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72. *Elife.* 2019;8.
15. Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Shlaifer I, Ayoubi R, Edwards AM, Durcan TM, et al. Identification of highly specific antibodies for Serine/threonine-protein kinase TBK1 for use in immunoblot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. *F1000Res.* 2022;11:977.
16. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Biddle MS, Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Bolivar SG, et al. Scaling of an antibody validation procedure enables quantification of antibody performance in major research applications. *Elife.* 2023;12.
17. Bandrowski A, Pairish M, Eckmann P, Grethe J, Martone ME. The Antibody Registry: ten years of registering antibodies. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2023;51(D1):D358-d67.
18. Bairoch A. The Cellosaurus, a Cell-Line Knowledge Resource. *J Biomol Tech.* 2018;29(2):25-38.
19. Stringer C, Wang T, Michaelos M, Pachitariu M. Cellpose: a generalist algorithm for cellular segmentation. *Nat Methods.* 2021;18(1):100-6.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	HTB-26	CVCL_0062	MDA-MB-231	WT
National Research Council Canada	-	CVCL_E8FU	MDA-MB-231	<i>CD44</i> KO
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC005968c010	CVCL_SH72	HAP1	<i>CD44</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the CD44 antibodies tested in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab101531**	GR319995-3	AB_10710025	recombinant mono	SP37	rabbit	0.01	Wb, FC
Abcam	ab189524**	GR3314218-10	AB_2885107	recombinant mono	EPR18668	rabbit	0.47	Wb, IP
Abcam	ab254530**	GR3317001-2	AB_2885131	recombinant mono	Hermes-3	mouse	0.54	Wb, IP, IF
Abcam	ab264539**	GR3341229-4	AB_2885133	recombinant mono	C44Mab-5	mouse	1.27	Wb, IP, FC
Abcam	ab51037**	GR3297534-13	AB_868936	recombinant mono	EPR1013Y	rabbit	1.92	Wb
ABclonal	A19020**	3522041554	AB_2862512	recombinant mono	ARC52411	rabbit	0.20	Wb, IF
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP1-47386*	D123476	AB_10010339	monoclonal	8E2F3	mouse	1.00	Wb, IP, IF, FC
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	BBA10*	BGR0120031	AB_356933	monoclonal	2C5	mouse	0.50	Wb, IP, FC
Cell Signaling Technology	3570*	10	AB_2076465	monoclonal	156-3C11	mouse	0.09	Wb, IP, IF, FC
Cell Signaling Technology	5640*	4	AB_10547133	monoclonal	8E2	mouse	NA	Wb, IP, IF, FC
Cell Signaling Technology	37259**	5	AB_2750879	recombinant mono	E7K2Y	rabbit	0.10	Wb
DSHB	CPTC-CD44-1**	2022-04-07	AB_2617229	recombinant mono	CPTC-CD44-1	rabbit	0.01	Wb
DSHB	CPTC-CD44-2*	2022-09-08	AB_2889957	monoclonal	CPTC-CD44-2	rabbit	0.02	NA
DSHB	H4C4*	2019-08-08	AB_528147	monoclonal	H4C4	mouse	0.07	Wb, IF, FC
DSHB	HERMES-1*	2022-03-03	AB_528148	monoclonal	HERMES-1	rat	0.03	Wb, IP, IF
DSHB	P1G12*	2018-11-15	AB_782201	monoclonal	P1G12/CRIII	mouse	0.01	Wb, IP, FC
GeneTex	GTX628472*	41113	AB_2888037	monoclonal	GT981	mouse	1.00	NA
GeneTex	GTX628895*	41232	AB_2888071	monoclonal	GT462	mouse	0.70	Wb, IP, FC
GeneTex	GTX637231**	44802	AB_3073944	recombinant mono	HL1650	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF, FC
Proteintech	15675-1-AP	78237	AB_2076198	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.27	Wb, IP, IF
Proteintech	60224-1-Ig*	10003281	AB_11042767	monoclonal	6F4H2	mouse	1.27	Wb, IP, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	14-0441-82*	2183528	AB_467246	monoclonal	IM7	rat	0.50	Wb, IP, IF, FC
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-13890*	YH383556	AB_10986810	monoclonal	156-3C11	mouse	0.20	Wb, IP, IF, FC

Wb=western blot; FC= flow cytometry; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, DSHB =Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, NA=not available

Table 3: Summary of the CD44 antibodies tested in flow cytometry

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab101531**	1047442-11	AB_10710025	recombinant mono	SP37	rabbit	0.056	Wb, FC
Abcam	ab189524**	1014086-31	AB_2885107	recombinant mono	EPR18668	rabbit	0.466	Wb, IP
Abcam	ab243894**	1004353-8	AB_3665133	recombinant mono	BLR038F	rabbit	0.050	Wb, IP, IF, FC
Abcam	ab254530**	1021378-21	AB_2885131	monoclonal	Hermes-3	mouse	0.989	Wb, IP, IF
Abcam	ab264539**	GR3341229-4	AB_2885133	monoclonal	C44Mab-5	mouse	1.266	Wb, IP, FC
Abcam	ab316123**	1078981-19	AB_3665134	recombinant poly	RM1084	rabbit	0.522	Wb, IF, FC
Abcam	ab51037**	1060629-5	AB_868936	recombinant mono	EPR1013Y	rabbit	2.075	Wb
BD Bioscience	550988*	3198146	AB_393999	monoclonal	515	mouse	0.500	FC
BD Bioscience	555476*	16104	AB_395868	monoclonal	G44-26	mouse	0.500	FC
Biolegend	163602**	B437862	AB_2892338	monoclonal	QA19A43	rat	0.500	FC
Biolegend	338802*	B264807	AB_1501199	monoclonal	BJ18	mouse	0.500	IF, FC
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP1-47386*	D123476-4	AB_10010339	monoclonal	8E2F3	mouse	1.000	Wb, IP, IF, FC
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	BBA10*	BGR0123031	AB_356933	monoclonal	2C5	mouse	0.500	Wb, IP, FC
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB7045*	CFQA0222051	AB_10973152	monoclonal	691534	mouse	0.500	Wb, IF, FC
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	BBA10*	BGR0123031	AB_356933	monoclonal	2C5	mouse	0.500	Wb, IP, FC
DSHB	CPTC-CD44-1**	2022-04-07	AB_2617229	recombinant mono	CPTC-CD44-1	rabbit	0.012	Wb
DSHB	CPTC-CD44-2*	2022-09-08	AB_2889957	monoclonal	CPTC-CD44-2	rabbit	0.020	NA
DSHB	H4C4*	2019-08-08	AB_528147	monoclonal	H4C4	mouse	0.065	Wb, IF, FC
DSHB	HERMES-1*	2022-03-03	AB_528148	monoclonal	HERMES-1	rat	0.025	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX628895*	41232	AB_2888071	monoclonal	GT462	mouse	0.700	Wb, IP, FC
GeneTex	GTX637231**	44802	AB_3073944	recombinant mono	HL1650	rabbit	1.000	Wb, IF, FC
Miltenyi	130-126-473**	5241100353	AB_2889581	recombinant mono	REA690	human	1.000	FC
ProteinTech	15675-1-AP	118645	AB_2076198	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.700	Wb, IP, IF
ProteinTech	60224-1-Ig*	10003281	AB_11042767	monoclonal	6F4H2	mouse	1.600	Wb, IP, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	14-0441-82*	2785616	AB_467246	monoclonal	IM7	rat	0.500	Wb, IP, IF, FC
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-41144**	YJ4089248B	AB_2898898	recombinant mono	ST57-03	rabbit	1.000	Wb

Wb=western blot; FC= flow cytometry; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody

Table 4: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all applications tested

Western blot	Immunoprecipitation
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Successful antibody</p> <p>Target protein not captured in the IP</p> </div> </div>	
Immunofluorescence	Flow cytometry
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>WT/KO cell mosaic</p> <p>Target protein not depleted in the KO</p> </div> </div>	

This table has been reproduced with permission from Ayoubi et al., Elife, 2023 (16)

A. MDA-MB-231

Figure 1: CD44 antibody screening by western blot (1/2)

B. HAP1

C. Lysis buffer: RIPA IP

Figure 1: CD44 antibody screening by western blot (2/2)

Figure 2: CD44 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (2/2)

Figure 3: CD44 antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Figure 4: CD44 antibody screening by cell surface flow cytometry (1/2)

Figure 4: CD44 antibody screening by cell surface flow cytometry (2/2)

Figure 5: CD44 antibody screening by intracellular flow cytometry (1/2)

Figure 5: CD44 antibody screening by intracellular flow cytometry (2/2)

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: CD44 antibody screening by western blot.

A) Lysates of MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated CD44 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab101531** at 1/1000, ab189524** at 1/1000, ab254530** at 1/5000, ab264539** at 1/1000, ab51037** at 1/5000, A19020** at 1/10 000, NBP1-47386* at 1/1000, BBA10* at 1/200, 3570* at 1/1000, 5640* at 1/1000, 37259** at 1/1000, CPTC-CD44-1** at 1/60 (0.2 µg/mL), CPTC-CD44-2** at 1/100, H4C4* at 1/325, HERMES-1* at 1/125, P1G12* at 1/55, GTX628472* at 1/500, GTX628895* at 1/500, GTX637231** at 1/500, 15675-1-AP at 1/5000, 60224-1-Ig* at 1/1000, 14-0441-82* at 1/500 and MA5-13890* at 1/200. **B)** Lysates of HAP1 WT and *CD44* KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with anti-CD44 ab189524** at 1/1000 and ab254530** at 1/5000. **C)** Protein extracts were prepared in RIPA buffer from MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO as well as in IP buffer from MDA-MB-231 WT. 30 µg of all lysates were processed for western blot with the anti-CD44 ab189524** diluted at 1/3000. Predicted band size: 81.5 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: CD44 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

MDA-MB-231 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed for 1 h using 0.2 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated CD44 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the CD44 antibody ab189524** used at 1/3000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=10% starting material; UB=10% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: CD44 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio on coverslips. Cells were stained with the indicated x antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (WT), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KO) channels was performed. Representative images of the merged blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/mL, and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilutions used: ab101531** at 1/50, ab189524** at 1/250, ab254530** at 1/500, ab264539** at 1/250, ab51037** at 1/1000, A19020** at 1/200, NBP1-47386* at 1/1000, BBA10* at 1/250, 3570* at 1/800, 37259** at 1/100,

CPTC-CD44-1** at 1/50, CPTC-CD44-2** at 1/50, H4C4* at 1/250, HERMES-1* at 1/250, P1G12* at 1/1000, GTX628895* at 1/700, GTX637231** at 1/1000, 15675-1-AP at 1/50, 60224-1-Ig* at 1/100 and MA5-13890* at 1/200. Bars = 10 µm. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 4: CD44 antibody screening by cell surface flow cytometry.

MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO cells were labelled with a green or violet, fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed in a 1:1 ratio. 400,000 cells were stained with the indicated CD44 antibodies and corresponding secondary antibodies. Antibody staining was quantified, and representative images showing the staining intensity in the KO population (pink histogram, dashed line) compared to the WT cells (green histogram, solid line) are presented. Histograms with dotted lines represent secondary antibody-only controls in both WT and KO cells. All primary antibodies were diluted to 1 µg/mL except for 14-0441-82* and 163602** which were 0.833 µg/mL and 0.665 µg/mL, respectively. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 5: CD44 antibody screening by intracellular flow cytometry.

MDA-MB-231 WT and *CD44* KO cells were labelled with a green or violet, fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed in a 1:1 ratio, fixed in 4% PFA and permeabilized in 0.1% saponin. 400,000 cells were stained with the indicated CD44 antibodies and corresponding secondary antibodies. Antibody staining was quantified, and representative images showing the staining intensity in the KO population (pink histogram, dashed line) compared to the WT cells (green histogram, solid line) are presented. Histograms with dotted lines represent secondary antibody-only controls in both WT and KO cells. All primary antibodies were diluted to 1 µg/mL except for 14-0441-82*, ab243894** and 163602** which were 0.833 µg/mL, 0.133 µg/mL and 0.665 µg/mL, respectively. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.